

Strengthening Communion among Catholic Students on Social Media: The Impact of Multicultural Experiences in the Digital Context

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Abstract: This study explored the meaning of multicultural experiences in building a community of Catholic students on social media. The context of social media was taken because they wanted to explore the multicultural struggles that built the community. The purpose of this study was to analyze the phenomenon of multicultural experiences on social media and foster inclusive relationships. Multicultural experience was a real step to address the ethnocentrism phenomenon that was developing at the time. The research methodology was qualitative, with an analytical descriptive method. Qualitative research was conducted using phenomenological analysis and interviews. Data analysis was carried out by observing the relational philosophy. The results of the analysis showed that multicultural experiences grew on social media and helped build a community. The multicultural experience was an anticipation for Catholic students so they did not get carried away by the spirit of ethnocentrism. Multicultural values became the norm for students in their use of social media. Social media became a place to give birth to multicultural values, such as accepting, respecting, and honoring differences. Multicultural experiences gave rise to an inclusive spirit in relating to others. The multicultural experience became a reflection for self-acceptance in living the diversity of Indonesia.

INTRODUCTION

The world was shaken by the Covid-19 pandemic, which caused many people to lose their lives. However, alongside this tragedy, new experiences emerged, one of which was the multicultural experience. A multicultural experience is a perspective that views human life as full of diversity and responds to that diversity (Lubis, 2015). It refers to the experience of the world's diverse life. This diversity is seen in various cultures encountered by society. Specifically, in the city of Malang, there are many higher education institutions, attracting people from various cultural backgrounds to pursue education there. Students from cultures ranging from Sumatra to Papua gather in Malang to study.

Multiculturalism is a concept aimed at building a nation that consists of various differences, such as ethnicity, race, religion, culture, language, and skin color, by respecting and honoring rights, including minority rights (Rosyada, 2014). A multicultural society is a form of modern society whose members come from various groups, ethnicities, races, religions, and cultures. They live together in a specific area, interacting directly or indirectly (Rusdiyanta & Syarbaini, 2009).

Multiculturalism acknowledges and appreciates diversity, transforming the social behavior of people in a pluralistic society (Danurahman et al., 2021). Social group, cultural, and ethnic differences are highly respected. A multicultural society strives for equality between minority and majority groups. Multiculturalism demands that people live with tolerance, mutual understanding between cultures and nations, in fostering a new world (Rusdiyanta & Syarbaini, 2009).

The key point of this research is to explore the multicultural experiences of Catholic students in as part of cultivating multicultural experiences on social media. Students tend to use social media more frequently as a means of communication and building relationships. It enables students to experience multicultural encounters through social media. The digital era today is inseparable from social media. Specifically, when the Covid-19 pandemic occurred, it presented a world different from before (Hardiman, 2021). The Covid-19 pandemic forced the global population to undergo a revolution, entering the digital world. Millennials have become witnesses to global digital civilization. Whether they like it or not, there has been a shift in how people relate to one another. Despite this, can humans foster a multicultural experience on social media? Or will humanity fall further into ethnocentrism and disregard others?

The challenges of multiculturalism in Indonesia consist of four elements: radicalism, ethnocentrism, boutique multiculturalism, and the state (Syam, 2009). These challenges have become more daunting as people now relate more through social media. It appears that ethnocentrism is a major obstacle to creating a multicultural culture. Ethnocentrism emphasizes the superiority of one's own culture while viewing other cultures negatively. This attitude is dangerous as it fosters division. Therefore, it is crucial for students to participate in fostering multicultural experiences. Multicultural experiences are a powerful weapon against ethnocentrism. Students, as the nation's future generation, are the hope for the country's future. The diverse reality of Indonesia is a value that must be preserved by students. A multicultural mentality must continuously be cultivated among students to create a harmonious Indonesia.

What is taught in the spirit of multiculturalism is not a spirit of uniformity (*tunggal ika*) that fosters strong unity, but rather emphasizes the recognition of the nation's cultural plurality (*bhinneka*), which better guarantees national unity toward democratic social renewal (Bukhori, 2019). Indonesia is being encouraged to embrace and live out multiculturalism. This must begin with the younger generation, particularly through social media.

A common phenomenon recently is the presence of individuals with an ethnocentric mindset. Furthermore, there is also the domination of the majority over the minority. Such phenomena lead to unrest and injustice. Ironically, this reality seems to be left unaddressed. Multicultural experiences also give rise to new social relationships. Particularly during the Covid-19 pandemic, these relationships were reflected on social media, even after the pandemic had subsided. Therefore, this study aims to explore the form of social relationships related to multicultural experiences on social media. Additionally, it seeks to uncover the steps taken by Catholic students to foster multicultural experiences on social media as a way to counter ethnocentrism.

Ethnocentrism poses a significant threat to relationships. Cultivating and understanding multicultural experiences provides an alternative way to combat ethnocentrism. Multicultural experiences lead to the spirit of inclusivism, which fosters tolerance and respect for others. Moreover, fostering multicultural experiences raises awareness among Indonesians to further develop the richness they already possess — the reality that Indonesia is plural.

In addition, understanding multiculturalism will make *communio*. *Communio* means paying attention to one another, having mutual belonging, giving to one another, supporting each other, advising, reminding, developing, serving, and striving to preserve the integrity of togetherness for the common happiness. This spirit, which promotes an inclusive understanding, is what the study aims to highlight and develop.

This research attempts to explain the meaning of multicultural experiences in building *communio* among Catholic students on social media. Therefore, it is important to identify the variables used in this study. At least five key terms are essential to understanding this research: multicultural, social media, ethnocentrism, *communio*, and inclusive. These five keywords serve as steps to understand the phenomena occurring in the lives of young Catholic people.

Multicultural is a term used to describe a person's perspective on the diversity of life in the world or cultural policies that emphasize acceptance of the reality of diversity and the various cultures in society, encompassing values, systems, customs, and politics they uphold (Suryana & Rusdiana, 2015). Social media is a platform for socializing between one person and another, conducted online, allowing people to interact and build relationships without limits—neither in terms of space nor time (Bhakti et al., 2018). Ethnocentrism refers to the idea held by individuals that their culture is superior to others, or the pride in their own culture while looking down on other cultures (Dianto, 2019). *Communio* refers to fellowship or togetherness experienced by people who believe in Christ. It means building together, so in daily life, it is crucial to share with one another. Inclusive means positioning oneself on equal footing with others, enabling the process of understanding different perspectives to resolve issues. The goal of inclusiveness is to create and foster an open environment that invites and includes everyone, regardless of differences in background, characteristics, abilities, status, condition, ethnicity, culture, and others. The spirit of inclusiveness aligns with *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika* (means: unity in diversity) lived by Indonesian society.

The appropriate solution that this study seeks to achieve is to cultivate the spirit of accepting, appreciating, and respecting differences. Multicultural experiences will foster an inclusive spirit in relationships with others. Specifically, social media becomes a powerful tool for spreading the “virus” of multiculturalism to everyone. This research invites readers to understand the struggles surrounding the multicultural experiences of Catholic students on social media.

METHOD

This research employs a qualitative approach with a descriptive-analytical writing method. Qualitative research involves data collection in a natural setting with the aim of interpreting the phenomena that occur. Qualitative research seeks to gain insight and understanding of a phenomenon and extrapolate it to similar situations. It emphasizes understanding social issues based on real-world conditions.

The qualitative research is deepened by conducting depth interviews. The descriptive-analytical method involves presenting the data obtained through research (interviews and questionnaires) and literature review to draw a conclusion. The conclusion in this article is based on data processing from interviews with Catholic students at the Indonesian School of Informatics and Computing (STIKI).

The research was conducted online via Zoom. The target audience is students and young people, aiming to cultivate an inclusive attitude, which involves appreciating differences and walking together as one. The research subjects are Catholic students at STIKI. Interviews were conducted with seven students. The interviews were conducted with seven Catholic students of STIKI Malang. The interviews took place on Sunday, May 21, 2023, and were conducted online using Zoom. The participants consisted of 4 male and 3 female students. Of the seven interviewees, 4 were from Javanese culture, 2 were from Chinese culture, and 1 from Manado culture.

The analysis in this research utilizes the concept of relationality. Relationality proposes a subject-to-subject relationship paradigm (Riyanto, 2020). Furthermore, the analysis is also based on Gus Dur's perspective on multiculturalism. Broadly speaking, this research is divided into three steps: data collection, data analysis, and generating new findings. This process will be presented in this research.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

From the interviews conducted with the participants about the meaning of multicultural experiences, most of them were familiar with the concept of multiculturalism. They shared the opinion that multicultural experiences involve differences between cultures, resulting in diversity in communal life. The interviewees stated that the main emphasis of multiculturalism lies in cultural, religious, economic, and ethnic differences, among others. In short, it refers to everything different in communal life within a certain place.

Based on the interviews, the participants expressed that multiculturalism or multicultural experiences have many positive values. The first respondent stated that multicultural experiences contain values of solidarity, respect, and mutual regard. The second respondent believed that tolerance toward communal life, which includes many differences, is a key value. The third respondent said that multiculturalism embodies diversity and tolerance. The fourth and fifth respondents shared the view that multiculturalism enhances solidarity amidst differences in ethnicity, religion, race, and culture. The sixth and seventh respondents agreed that multicultural experiences provide an opportunity for everyone to learn to understand and accept the strengths and weaknesses of those around them. From the

explanations above, it can be concluded that all participants agreed that multiculturalism has many positive values that can be gained in communal life within society.

The participants each had different opinions about the challenges and struggles they faced in their multicultural experiences. The first and second respondents revealed that there is a tendency for exclusive behavior, as one culture might be considered superior to another. The third respondent stated that the greatest challenge is the differences in values and principles upheld by each culture. The fourth respondent felt that the biggest struggle in multicultural experiences is the potential for disagreements due to differences in background. The fifth respondent mentioned that the dominance of one culture over another can result in disharmony. The sixth respondent believed that the biggest struggle in multicultural experiences is the lack of respect for others who are different. The final respondent felt that isolation may occur because some people struggle to socialize with more dominant cultures, leaving non-dominant cultures feeling alienated.

According to the interviews, the participants saw various forms of multiculturalism on social media. The first respondent mentioned that social media is a platform to learn about diverse multicultural experiences, as seen in the abundance of cultural content on social media. The second respondent said that multiculturalism is evident on social media through the use of different languages in captions across various platforms. The third respondent noted that multiculturalism on social media can be seen in the variety of vocabulary encountered, such as from Batak Toba, Javanese, Mentawai, and other languages. The fourth respondent believed that multiculturalism on social media is also displayed through photo or video posts showcasing certain cultural traditions or customs. The fifth and sixth respondents agreed that multiculturalism is reflected in various forms of art, such as cultural artifacts like songke fabric or ulos. The last respondent stated that multiculturalism can be seen in the content of dances and music from local customs, like the *Barongsai* dance, *Gawi*, and others.

The interviews with the participants revealed that ethnocentrism is the belief that one's culture is superior to others. This is due to narrow-mindedness and a lack of openness to other cultures. This attitude ultimately leads to conflict between different groups or cultures. However, one respondent mentioned that ethnocentrism is not very dangerous if its purpose is academic, for mutual understanding of other cultures. Nevertheless, it becomes extremely dangerous if the goal is to dominate other cultures and regard one's own culture as the best. This can lead to cultural conflicts between different groups.

Regarding the interpretation of multicultural experiences through social media, the respondents believe that when someone wishes to foster a multicultural experience, they need to have an open attitude towards certain cultures. This openness can be manifested by participating in various discussion activities. The second respondent believes that there is a need for various academic studies on culture to be highlighted on social media so that others can better understand certain cultures. The third respondent suggests that building relationships with people from different cultures is important. This approach helps individuals become more familiar with both the similarities and differences between cultures. The fourth respondent

states that there should be mutual respect between different cultures. The fifth respondent mentions that in order to foster multicultural experiences, people need to introduce their own cultural practices on social media. This is intended so that others can become familiar with their culture. The sixth respondent believes that there is a need for empathy and a spirit of sharing cultural richness with other cultures. The final respondent emphasizes the importance of appreciating both one's own culture and others' cultures without any inclination to demean any particular culture.

Based on interviews conducted with seven Catholic students of STIKI-Malang, it can be concluded that they have a basic understanding of multiculturalism and ethnocentrism. Multicultural experiences refer to the differences between cultures, which create diversity in communal life. Such experiences are born from an attitude and spirit of tolerance amid various differences. However, multicultural attitudes are often overshadowed by ethnocentrism, which can lead to division in society.

Ethnocentrism is an attitude that leads someone to a radical understanding that considers their own culture superior to others. This eventually makes it difficult for someone to appreciate other cultures outside of their own (Hamdani, 2022). Ethnocentrism has a very destructive impact on communal life, resulting in conflict. Such a mindset leads to division because it creates a gap in communal living. Rather than being seen as a unifying force, differences are viewed as divisive.

For the seven respondents, who are Catholic students at STIKI-Malang, they have also experienced ethnocentrism through social media. Their position as a minority among a majority presents its own crisis, particularly in terms of identity. Being a minority in a majority context not only leads to an identity crisis but also induces fear. This frequently happens on social media, where conflicts between majority and minority groups can be found. For instance, when minorities post content related to their religion or culture, they often receive negative comments. This ultimately fosters division and conflict in society. Excessive ethnocentrism like this will negatively impact the development of both individuals and groups within the community.

Today, many conflicts arise due to a lack of solidarity and mutual respect between religions or cultures. For example, the conflict that occurred in Central Kalimantan some time ago between Dayak and Madurese ethnic groups. This conflict started due to economic competition. According to the *Denny JA Foundation*, hundreds of people were recorded as having died in the conflict (Welianto, 2020). Such cases are not new in society. Therefore, social media can serve as a means to build relationships to learn about different religions, cultures, and traditions. However, social media can also be a tool for undermining certain cultures or religions (Mukhamad, 2020). Wisdom is needed in using social media so that it can become a bridge for people to learn about each other's cultures or religions.

Multiculturalism is a social and cultural understanding of individuals or groups. This understanding can be built through deep relationships with others, which can be facilitated through social media. This needs to be done continuously to ensure that tolerance in communal

life is always maintained among social media users and society (Sipuan et al., 2022). Multiculturalism has a tremendous impact on human life. It is a consequence of the plurality of society, which can be seen through differences in religion, race, ethnicity, occupation, and culture. Multicultural experiences are something to be grateful for in communal life. Pluralism demands the achievement of mutual respect, appreciation, and tolerance amid differences (Suradi, 2018). Multiculturalism fosters a sense of nationalism, or love for one's own country. With such a spirit, it becomes possible for everyone to appreciate and accept those who are different from them.

Social media today is no longer unfamiliar to people of all ages, from children to adults. Everyone can have their own social media platforms, such as Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, and many more. People have their own ways of using social media—whether for business, making connections, entertainment, or acquiring knowledge. The presence of social media in today's world serves many functions and benefits. Therefore, social media can also be used as a tool to introduce or promote culture, allowing people to learn about various cultures both in Indonesia and beyond.

Many people use social media as a means to introduce their culture, whether they are aware of it or not when posting content. This is evident on platforms like Instagram, where various posts and comments related to culture are easily found. This represents a form of multicultural experience in the use of social media.

The multicultural experience in social media use needs to be continuously reflected upon as a means to appreciate and listen to various cultures. Reflecting on and listening to culture means demonstrating an attitude of sensitivity and openness toward cultures outside of one's own. This attitude of listening also reflects a readiness to accept the strengths and weaknesses of a particular culture. By reflecting on multicultural experiences in this way, tolerance in communal life—both in social media and everyday life—will grow.

Catholic students at STIKI-Malang also have their own multicultural experiences. Based on interviews with the seven respondents, it is clear that they consistently strive to appreciate every multicultural experience they encounter through social media. This is reflected in their ability to accept differences in various cultures (Najmina, 2018). For example, they show this by liking or leaving positive comments on social media posts and distancing themselves from ethnocentric attitudes that consider their own culture superior to others.

When multicultural experiences are fully appreciated, they help build communion among young Catholics. Communion can be fostered through social media, which has become a significant part of the lives of Catholic youth. Efforts to counter violent and intolerant religious expressions can be made by reviving the spirituality of religion. This spirituality is the essence of religion, offering three key elements: love, peace, and cooperation (Sarbin, 2017). The spirit of tolerance requires respect for differences in a pluralistic society. Tolerance does not arise automatically; it requires education and nurturing. With proper education and nurturing of tolerance, Catholic youth can build communion through social media.

The Church, as a compassionate community, can manifest this compassion through social media (Nugroho & Firmanto, 2022). This is possible when people have a caring attitude toward one another. The future of the Church lies in the hands of the youth (Putra & Firmanto, 2022). It is only fitting that the youth foster compassion to create an inclusive environment. Inclusivity becomes a welcoming space for newcomers, reflecting a Church that is present within the community. Differences in ethnicity, race, religion, and social groups are excellent social assets for realizing unity (Firmanto, 2017). Therefore, differences should not be a reason for conflict in communal life, but rather a unifying force that enriches shared life.

Indonesia is a country rich in natural resources. However, aside from that, Indonesia also has a vast array of cultures, each with its unique characteristics and differences from one another (Munif, 2018). The diversity and differences that exist within Indonesia should be viewed and understood as a blessing in communal life, not the opposite.

Catholic students at STIKI-Malang, through their multicultural experiences on social media, can foster a sense of community. Social media serves as a medium to reflect on multicultural experiences while also building communion, which ultimately leads to an experience of faith (Susilo & Pasi, 2023). This multicultural experience can be interpreted as a mysterious encounter between human faith and the divine. Faith experience is the result of analyzing human experiences, especially those of the youth, which involve the limitations and mysteries of human existence (Firmanto, 2016). The faith experiences of Catholic students at STIKI-Malang can be lived out through their engagement with social media. It is on these platforms that they cultivate both multicultural experiences and communion.

The concept of multiculturalism is one that can address the challenges of a changing era. Multiculturalism is like an ideology that elevates or celebrates cultural differences, or a belief that acknowledges and encourages the realization of cultural pluralism as a way of life in society (Ranubaya & Endi, 2024; Tari et al., 2021). Multiculturalism will serve as a bond and a bridge that accommodates differences, including ethnic differences, in a multicultural society (Ambarudin, 2016). This concept helps individuals see differences as a blessing in communal life.

CONCLUSION

The multicultural experiences among Catholic students of STIKI in Malang can foster communion within social media. Communion is essential for nurturing the faith of Catholic youth. The biggest challenge to multiculturalism is combating the phenomenon of ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism can be overcome on social media through multicultural experiences. These experiences give rise to a spirit of self-acceptance, tolerance, and inclusiveness.

Social media serves as the primary platform for sharing cultural richness with everyone, allowing people to gain insight and knowledge to assess reality more wisely. Multicultural experience is a wealth that Indonesia possesses. Students who can appreciate multiculturalism are individuals capable of building communion to live in mutual sharing with others.

Differences should be understood as blessings from God, serving as a means to unite all of Indonesian society.

Communion through social media is a step toward building catechesis and nurturing the faith of Catholic youth. This is the breakthrough needed by young people today. Communion is crucial because it can unite multiculturalism into an inclusive spirit. This inclusive spirit must be instilled from an early age so that future generations truly understand multiculturalism and can maintain harmony and unity in communal life.

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